

Reflect array Antenna based on Torus ring Unit cell for X –Band Application

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Abstract – A single layer tiny reflect-array antenna is presented here based on Torus ring patch for X band applications which operates at the frequency band from 8 GHz to 12 GHz. The linear phase range of 0 to 350° is obtained. A 10*10 reflect array antenna is designed using single layer micro strip array with the size of 25 mm * 25 mm .The computer simulation technology(CST) software is used for simulation of the whole reflect array antenna on the Rogers 5880 substrate with dielectric constant of 2.2 and a thickness of 1.6 mm . The designed reflect array antenna is validated by analysing 2-D and 3-D radiation pattern and gain.

Keywords - Reflect array, Single layer , Torus ring patch, CST.

I.INTRODUCTION

The reflect array antenna is a combination of reflector and phased array with some features of both antennas. Micro strip reflect arrays are flat reflector antennas consisting of a planar array of micro strip patches illuminated by a feed . Reflect arrays are an innovative and attractive alternative to the conventional reflector antennas[1] . Printed RA antennas have widely been used for smart arrays and beamforming is achieved by regulating amplitude and phase of each element [2] Advances in Wireless technologies and Telecommunication require the deployment of low cost, light weight, high gain and easy to install micro strip antennas reflect arrays is largely diffused in many application fields such as remote sensing and satellite communications [3] .The reflecting surface is irradiated spatially using a suitable feed antenna. One important issue in the design of microstrip reflect arrays is obtaining wide phasing range and slow phase variations(slope) as a function of the phasing element's variable size. A wide phase range gives the designer more flexibility in selecting proper element sizes for a given phase value [4]. A horn antenna for feeding purpose along with an array of radiating elements together constitutes the general structure of reflectarray antenna.Due to nature of spatial

illumination of the incident wave onto elements by the horn, path differences exist and hence phase differences exist which need to be compensated for each element by varying their resonant dimensions[5]. Recent developments in cubesat satellite technology have enabled easier and relatively inexpensive access to space. One of the major requirements of cubesats is small size which hinders the use of large high gain antennas[6]. An antenna consisting of a feed and an array of reflecting elements arranged on a surface and adjusted so that the reflected waves from the individual elements combine to produce a prescribed secondary radiation pattern. The incident spherical wave is transformed into linear wave fronts in a parabolic reflector, the phase necessary to produce a collimated beam is compensated by the parabolic form[7]. The high gain feature of the RA antenna becomes inherent due to the large number of elements on the array. This high gain has made RAs suitable and attractive for space and sat-com applications. RAs can be installed flexibly and have a low cost. The linear phase shift is achieved by varying geometrical parameters of the unit cell element. On this reflecting surface, there is an array of passive printed elements each with its own specific dimension in order to compensate the phase difference caused by the feed to element path and thus produce a co-phased plane and hence the directive pattern at the antenna far field region[8].

II. UNIT ELEMENT DESIGN AND ANALYSIS

The reflectarray unit cell element is designed using a microstrip Torus ring patch which resonates at 10 GHz. However, compact single layer elements with large linear phase range are the desirable characteristics. This has been achieved by varying the radius of the unit cell element. The unit cell consists of a torus ring patch for the lower band on the Rogers substrate with permittivity 2.2 and thickness 1.6 mm. The performance of the proposed unit cell is determined in terms of phase range and effect of incident angles, different frequencies, substrate thickness have been discussed, The incident angle does not have any change in the phase range.

Fig 1. Single Unit cell Structure
Dimension: Outer radius – 5 mm , Inner radius – 3 mm

Fig 2. Return loss parameter S11

Fig 3. Phase Reflection Curve

III. FULL REFLECTARRAY CONFIGURATION

Fig 4. Perspective Layout of Reflectarray Antenna

A ten * ten elements centre-fed reflectarray is simulated and measured on Rogers 5880 substrate as shown in Figure. At the bottom layer, Ground plane is constructed then substrate of Rogers 5880 of dielectric constant 2,2 with a thickness of 1.6 mm is kept over the ground plane and then torus ring patch is etched on the substrate. Uniform spacing of 0.5λ is provided between 100 elements. The complete reflectarray system simulations are carried out CST software. The reflectarray model consists of finite number of elements. These elements have uniform sizes according to phase distribution of array aperture.

IV.RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

The simulations are carried out in Time domain solver and E field, H field and far fields are added in field monitors to generate output of far field radiation pattern at 8 GHz,10 GHz and 12 GHz respectively. The gain is measured with E_{max} , H_{max} and power flow.S11 is -0.35 db at 9.7 GHz. Realized gain at 8 GHz is 57.36 db and at 10 GHz is 132.2 db and at 12 GHz is 193.9 db. The power distribution curve is also plotted. Full reflect array configuration with 100 torus elements in a 10*10 array is shown in Fig 4. excited by the horn antenna working in X band.

Fig 5. Radiation pattern for the proposed Reflectarray antenna at 8 GHz

Fig 6. Radiation pattern for the proposed Reflectarray antenna at 10 GHz

Fig 7. Radiation pattern for the proposed Reflectarray antenna at 12 GHz

Fig

Fig 8. Power Distribution curves

V. CONCLUSION

A novel torus ring patch reflectarray element and a 10*10 reflectarray antenna has been proposed in this paper. A 10*10 reflectarray antenna has been designed using a proposed element and its return loss, phase performance is plotted. The proposed antenna provides maximum gain of 132.2 db at centre frequency of 10 GHz. The future scope of the antenna lies in satellite communication applications like DBS, Disaster management, radar system, remote sensing and endless applications which require high gain antennas.

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